

CRACK ONSET IN A POLYMER MATRIX WITH OPEN-HOLE CONFIGURATION AND VISCOELASTIC BEHAVIOR. APPLICATION OF THE FINITE FRACTURE MECHANICS COUPLED CRITERION

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ABSTRACT

Fracture of open-hole polymer (PMMA) plates under tension is addressed by the coupled stress-energy criterion of Finite Fracture Mechanics (FFM). The stress and energy conditions were calculated using Finite Elements (FE) simulations, the PMMA being modeled as a linear viscoelastic material in the glassy state (23°C).

The viscoelastic Generalized Maxwell-Wiechert material model was employed, its computational implementation being done in the ANSYSTM software by means of Prony series. The Prony series final parameters were obtained by means of a nonlinear minimum squares approximation to the experimental data, taken from tensile tests carried out with several strain rates. The incremental Energy Release Rate was calculated using an instantaneous “incremental Crack Closure method”. Predictions of the size effect on the critical load obtained, for the plates with holes, are compared with experimental results.

1 INTRODUCTION

It is well known that the composite material polymeric matrices have a viscoelastic behaviour, being best modeled by nonlinear viscoelastic models, due to the normally higher loads involved in structures made of composite materials [1]. In this work, fracture of a polymer matrix is studied. The material used is the Polymethyl Methacrylate (PMMA). The aim is also to extend the present work, to other polymer matrices used in composites, like epoxy resin.

Figure 1: Plate with hole analyzed: a) Geometry and loadings, b) Symmetrical crack onset.

The studies of crack onset in brittle materials often lay on the Finite Fracture Mechanics (FFM) theory [2-3].

The present work, is a further development of the study of crack onset in a PMMA plate with hole in tension (see Figure 1), by FFM, already addressed in previous works [4-6], but now modeling the material as linear viscoelastic.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

2.1 Tensile tests at several velocities

Several PMMA tensile, straight and dog bone, coupons were tested at cross head velocities of 0.5, 5 and 15 mm/min [5-6]. The tests done with velocity 5 mm/min are the ones that respect the standard ASTM D638-03 [7], in order to obtain PMMA elastic properties. Due to some fabrication limitations and difficulties only the tests for 5 and 15 mm/min were made with the geometry (type III), indicated in that standard, in a number of five specimens each. For the 0.5 mm/min, only straight specimens were able to be machined and tested and only two specimens, of the five tested, were valid. In Figure 2a) is shown a type III PMMA dog bone instrumented coupon after rupture, and in b) the engineering stress-strain curves, for the several test velocities, are depicted. The PMMA average fracture stress, obtained with the standard coupons, was 63.4 MPa.

Figure 2: PMMA tensile tests at several velocities: a) Tensile coupon being tested, b) Engineering Stress-Strain plots for test velocities of 0.5, 5 and 15 mm/min.

2.2 Load/unloading tests at several velocities

In Figure 3 the load and unloading is shown versus load cell displacement curves of PMMA specimens in tension, for several velocities: 0.5, 5 and 15 mm/min. Some hysteresis effect typical in polymers, which indicates their viscoelastic behaviour, can be seen.

The area inside each load/unload cycle represents the energy retained inside the material, after the unloading, which is converted into heat. In metals all the energy is recovered because the unloading curve follows the previous loading curve.

The fact that in each unloading, for the present case, the curve did not return to the origin, should be due to the fact that the specimen was not left resting at that point and the loading was continued. This impeded the restoration of the zero load-displacement state.

Figure 3: Loading and unloading of PMMA tensile specimens at several test velocities: a) 0.5 mm/min , b) 5 mm/min and c) 15 mm/min.

2.3 Fracture tests

PMMA fracture properties were obtained according to ASTM D5045-07 [8], which is aimed to calculate fracture toughness in polymers and plastics in general. The specimen type used was Single Edge Notch Bending (SENB). The natural crack, as in plastics, cannot be obtained by fatigue, thus it was made by tapping a fresh blade into the notch. A blade holder was fabricated for this operation. The average PMMA sheet thickness was 7.45 mm. In Figure 4a) the blade holder is depicted in position to be tapped with a hammer, in order to create a natural crack. In Figure 4b) one can see SENB specimen tested.

In order to calculate the critical Energy Release Rate, is necessary to test equally prepared, un-cracked, specimens for correction of indentation at loading points, specimen compression and system compliance. The test is performed at the same cross head displacement rate and approximately at the same load level, as the fracture specimens. These tests yielded load-displacement curves whose strain energy was subtracted to the cracked specimens strain energy. The number of valid specimens tested was three for the cracked and un-cracked types. More specimens were made but they were invalid due to the crack size being out of the range of standard values. The final critical Energy Release Rate obtained was $G_{Ic} = 487 \text{ J/m}^2$.

Figure 4: SENB specimen preparation and testing: a) Natural crack obtention, b) SENB specimen tested.

2.4 Plates with holes rupture tests

In order to study the crack onset in plates with holes, rupture tests in these plates were done. The dimensions of the open hole plates according to the nomenclature of Figure 1a) are $W = 40$ mm, $L = 300$ mm, and hole diameters $2R = 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4.25, 7$ and 10 mm. The plate thickness, t , was between 7.4 and 8.8 mm, due to plate thickness variation [6]. Five coupons for each diameter were fabricated. The rupture occurred suddenly and no visible plasticity was detected. Some of the broken specimens are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Ruptured PMMA holed specimens with diameters: a) 3mm, b) 7 mm and c) 10 mm.

3 VISCOELASTIC MODEL OF PMMA

A material is said to be viscoelastic if its stress response consists of an elastic part and viscous part. Upon application of a load, the elastic response is instantaneous while the viscous part occurs over time [9]. From the previous tests done with PMMA tensile coupons, at several velocities (Figure 2b) and Figure 3), it can be seen that PMMA has a viscoelastic behavior, due mainly to the internal energy consumption visible when unloaded. The PMMA viscoelastic model used in this work is based on a Maxwell-Wiechert model, depicted in Figure 6, having springs to model the elastic part and dashpots to model the viscous one. In the referenced figure, E is the spring stiffness, if one substitutes force, F , by F/A (A is the area of the spring element) and the change in length, ΔL , by the strain $\Delta L/L$. E_∞ is

the equilibrium modulus. The damper viscosity is η , and τ_i are the relaxation times equal to the damper viscosity divided by the spring stiffness, $\tau_i = \eta/E$.

This viscoelastic generalized model was chosen due to its capacity to model a real polymer, since it can have several elements, leading to a better approximation of the multiple molecular elements, with several sizes, relaxing differently, that real polymers have. This model is equivalent to a Generalized Maxwell model (several Maxwell serial spring – damper elements mounted in parallel) substituting one of its elements with a simple spring. In literature it is called also only Wiechert model or also, in a broad sense, Generalized Maxwell model, due perhaps to the fact that its basis is a Maxwell model with one of the elements substituted by a spring. The true Generalized Maxwell model should approximate better the thermoplastics and the Maxwell-Wiechert should do a better approximation of the thermoset polymers. This is due to the fact that in the former, without the spring in parallel, E_∞ , the stress would decay to a zero value, (fact observed experimentally in the thermoplastics), rather than decay to a finite value like in the latter case of thermosets [10-11]. In the present work one has used, as preliminary study, the model having a non-zero equilibrium modulus.

Figure 6: Viscoelastic Maxwell-Wiechert model representation, with springs and dashpots.

ANSYSTM has the option of modeling viscoelasticity, using this general model, by means of a Dirichlet–Prony series, or simply Prony series, which are an analytical form used to represent relaxation functions, a finite sum of individual decaying exponentials in time [12]. These series take the form, for the shear relaxation function:

$$G(t) = G_\infty + \sum_{i=1}^{n_G} G_i \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_i^G}} \quad (1)$$

where G_∞ is the equilibrium shear modulus, G_i are the individual shear relaxation modulus, t , the time, τ_i^G , the relaxation times and n_G , the number of Prony terms. In ANSYSTM one has to work with the relative modulus:

$$\alpha_i^G = \frac{G_i}{G_0} \quad (2)$$

Thus equation (1) takes the form:

$$G(t) = G_0 \left\{ \alpha_\infty^G + \sum_{i=1}^{n_G} \alpha_i^G \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_i^G}} \right\} \quad (3)$$

where G_0 is the modulus for time equal to zero,

$$G_0 = G_\infty + \sum_{i=1}^{n_G} G_i \quad (4)$$

For the volumetric compressibility modulus K the same equations (1-4) are used by substituting G by K . The relaxation elastic modulus, E , also follows equation (1), substituting G by E .

One term Prony series was assumed for the present initial model. The needed input values for the elastic part are: E_0 and the Poisson ratio ν . In this study one assume a constant Poisson coefficient of 0.34, obtained from the experimental static tests. For the viscous part one needs to input the relative modulus for shear and bulk, $\alpha_i^G = \alpha_i^K$ and the relaxation times, $\tau_i^G = \tau_i^K$.

These parameters were obtained from the experimental stress-strain data indicated in Figure 2, assuming that the temporal elasticity modulus, $\hat{E}(t)$, to be fitted to the experimental data, is given by the following integral of the relaxation modulus:

$$\hat{E}(t) = \int_0^t E(t) dt \quad (5)$$

We can write a “temporal” Hooke’s Law, using the strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}$:

$$\sigma(t, \dot{\epsilon}) = \hat{E}(t) \dot{\epsilon} \quad (6)$$

The time can be given by the following expression:

$$t = \epsilon(t) / \dot{\epsilon} \quad (7)$$

Substitution of the latter in the expression for temporal stress, equation (6), yields:

$$\sigma(\epsilon/\dot{\epsilon}, \dot{\epsilon}) = \hat{E}(\epsilon/\dot{\epsilon}) \dot{\epsilon} \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma(\epsilon/\dot{\epsilon}, \dot{\epsilon}) / \dot{\epsilon} = \hat{E}(\epsilon/\dot{\epsilon}) \quad (9)$$

Using the last expression, the experimental stress and strain were divided, for each test velocity, by the strain rate respecting to that velocity, in order to have a common factor to all curves (see Figure 7a) and a detail of the origin zone Figure 7b)). This sort of graphic permits to make dimensionless all the experimental data in terms of time, in abscissas.

Figure 7: Stress-strain experimental curves, divided by the strain rate, for several test velocities: a) general view, b) Detail view of the initial part of the curves relative to 15 and 5 mm/min velocity.

Using, in this initial work, only one curve of each of the 5 and 15 mm/min velocity data, a sorted cloud of points was gathered for the common zone, from $t = 0$ up to $t = 10$ s (data of 15mm/min) and up to approximately 23 s (data of 5 mm/min). The cloud of points can be seen as circles in Figure 8a). In this first model we have not used the data from the 0.5 mm/min velocity.

Figure 8: Obtaining the viscoelastic data: a) Experimental cloud of points and the approximating function fit, b) Viscoelastic relaxation temporal modules.

The abscissas values in Figure 8a) were named x_{data} and the ordinates, y_{data} . One can obtain the temporal elastic modulus, $\hat{E}(t)$, by fitting a nonlinear curve passing those points. That fitting was achieved by means of Nonlinear Least Squares curve fit in MATLABTM. First, one needs to obtain the expression for the approximating function, $\hat{E}(t)$, which is accomplished by integrating $E(t)$ in time, equation (5). $E(t)$ has the form indicated in the following equation:

$$E(t) = E_{\infty} + \sum_{i=1}^N E_i \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_i}} \quad (10)$$

Integrating in time it yields:

$$\hat{E}(t) = E_{\infty}t + \sum_{i=1}^N E_i\tau_i \left[1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_i}} \right] \quad (11)$$

The terms $E_i\tau_i$ can be named ε_i . The minimum least squares function, composed by the squared difference of ordinates of the approximating function and the experimental data points, for one Prony series term, is given by:

$$J(E_{\infty}, \varepsilon_i, \tau_i) = \sum_{i=1}^M \left[\left[p_1 x_{data} + p_2 \left(1 - e^{-\frac{x_{data}}{p_3}} \right) \right] - y_{data} \right]^2 \quad (12)$$

Where the time, t , has been named x_{data} and the parameters to be found are $p_1 = E_{\infty}$, $p_2 = E_1\tau_1$ and $p_3 = \tau_1$. MATLABTM, applies automatically the squares and minimizes it, yielding the three unknown parameters. In Figure 8a) one can also see the approximating function $\hat{E}(t)$ fitting the data points. After having the parameters of the approximating function one can plot the relaxation moduli: the elastic, $E(t)$, the shear, $G(t) = E(t)/2(1 + \nu)$ and the bulk, $K(t) = E(t)/3(1 - 2\nu)$.

To obtain the first Prony elastic relaxation term one has to calculate: $E_1 = p_2/p_3$. In Figure 8b), the viscoelastic relaxation temporal moduli are plotted.

If one multiplies the approximating function, $\hat{E}(t)$, ordinate values by the strain rate, one obtains the approximating stress (equation (8)). In Figure 9, this function is plotted having strains in abscissa and is compared with experimental results. It can be seen that it approximates quite well the curves of 5 and 15 mm/min. With reference to the 0.5 mm/min velocity curve, as its points were not contemplated in the approximating parameters obtention, this curve is not so well correlated. At the hole border the stress concentration is around 3, so it is important to capture the three times more elevated velocity stresses and strains, respective to the standard test at 5 mm/min. That was the reason for not having included the 0.5 mm/min data in the viscoelastic study.

Figure 9: Stress-Strain curves comparison, for several test velocities, between experimental tests and viscoelastic approximation function.

The elastic parameters obtained from the fitting were: $E_0 = 4080$ MPa and the Poisson ratio $\nu = 0.34$, already known. The viscoelastic parameters obtained were: Prony series relative modulus, $\alpha_1^G = \alpha_1^K = 0.459$ and the relaxation times, $\tau_1^G = \tau_1^K = 10.78$ s. They were then introduced in ANSYS™ in order to pursue with the coupled criterion calculation, addressed in the next section.

4 FINITE FRACTURE MECHANICS (FFM) COUPLED CRITERION AND ITS COMPUTATIONAL IMPLEMENTATION FOR THE VISCOELASTIC CASE

4.1 The FFM in general form

A coupled criterion, which combines energy and stress conditions [2], has been used here in order to predict the remote stress needed to originate the onset of two transverse symmetrical cracks, at the hole border (see Figure 1). The displacement control is assumed.

Stress criterion:

The stress criterion assumes the onset of cracks when the vertical component of the stresses near the hole, σ_y , along the symmetry axis of the plate (x), for $0 \leq \ell \leq \ell_c$, is higher or equal than the critical stress σ_c (material tensile strength):

$$\sigma_y(\ell) \geq \sigma_c, \quad 0 \leq \ell \leq \ell_c \quad (13)$$

Energy criterion:

The energetic criterion is given by the following condition, involving the incremental and critical Energy Release Rate:

$$G_{inccrem} = -\frac{\Delta\Pi}{\Delta A} \geq G_c, \quad \Delta\Pi = \Pi_2 - \Pi_1 \quad (14)$$

where $\Delta\Pi$ is the instantaneous decrease of the stored elastic strain energy due an instantaneous crack advance at each side of the plate hole (see Figure 1). ΔA is the variation of crack area and G_c is the critical Energy Release Rate.

4.2 The FFM coupled criterion for the linear case

The coupled criterion, for the linear elastic material model case, can be calculated semianalytically [4-6]. The stress criterion condition uses Kirsch's solution to calculate σ_y , in order to be used in the stress condition (13) with the equal sign, and ascertain it for several fictitious crack sizes. The energetic part of the coupled criterion uses the incremental form of Griffith's energy balance condition. By

coupling the two conditions in one equation and solve it by numerical integration, it is possible to obtain the critical remote tensile stress and crack size at onset for the case of the plate with hole [5-6].

4.3 The FFM coupled criterion for linear viscoelastic material model

In order to calculate the critical combination of the crack length, after its onset, at the hole and the remote stress applied to the top border of the plate, for the viscoelastic case, two separate Finite Element (FE) models were made in ANSYSTM software. The viscoelastic material properties were inserted by means of Prony series coefficients as indicated in the past section. The elements used were plane solid quadratic shape function elements (PLANE183).

The first model was composed of a plate with a hole (situation of Figure 1a)) and was used to compute the *Stress criterion*. The second FE model, with hole and crack, was used to address the *Energy criterion*. In the present viscoelastic case, the instantaneous decrease of the stored elastic strain energy, $\Delta\Pi$, is calculated by the method based on Irwin's Crack Closure Integral, called Crack Closure Method or two-step crack closure technique [13], that will be detailed ahead. The fundamental issue here is to consider an instantaneous crack onset and closure.

In both cases, a one quarter FE model of the holed plate (due to symmetry), restrained by symmetrical constraints, was loaded incrementally with several displacement steps, u_{nom} , (see Figure 1, shown as a full model) until a final displacement of 3.9 mm. This displacement value is a reference of the full plate total displacement obtained in experimental tests, divided by two (half plate displacement). Twenty incrementation displacement steps were computed, dividing thus the total time by a factor of twenty. The viscoelastic model followed the real test time duration and thus had the same velocity (5 mm/min). For a quarter FE model, the half specimen displacement per minute was half of the 5 mm (2.5 mm) that the total specimen would do in one minute, for that input velocity. The half specimen displaced with half of the velocity, maintaining the same strain rate. The half FE model displaced the 3.9 mm of input increments in a total time of: $(3.9 \text{ mm}) \times \frac{60 \text{ s}}{2.5 \text{ mm}} = 93.6 \text{ s}$.

Figure 10: FE mesh and constraints for the plate with hole, $2R = 0.5 \text{ mm}$ and crack of 0.01 mm :
a) General mesh (rotated view), b) Node coupling at top line, c) Detail of the hole and opened crack.

The nonlinear solution was solved with typical Newton-Raphson ANSYSTM options. In order to simplify FE work, the mesh of the holed plate without open cracks (1st FE model) was the same as the mesh having opened cracks (2nd FE model), the crack line being restrained vertically in the 1st model, in order to simulate a plate having just a hole. The mesh was made in parametric form, using MATLABTM routines and Ansys Parametric Design Language (APDL), with full control of line divisions and geometric progression spaces (element size progressive reduction), having in this

manner a satisfactory control on mesh refinement near the hole and crack. As an example, a FE mesh and constraints not applied to the crack (2nd FE model), for a hole of 0.5 mm and crack 0.01 mm, can be seen in Figure 10a). The incremental displacement was input via a master node, which was coupled with the remainder nodes of the top plate line (see Figure 10b)). The total resultant vertical reaction load of the master node and input displacements were recorded into an array.

Stress criterion:

For this case, besides having the load and displacement of the master node, referred previously, one needed to have the stress σ_y , at the potential crack path line, emanating from the hole, in order to apply the stress condition (13) and find the remote applied stress, σ_∞ , for several cracks sizes.

Figure 11: Scheme of the arrays obtained in ANSYS™ for: a) Stress criterion, b) Energy criterion.

Thus, the nodal stresses σ_y and horizontal (x) node coordinates (fictious crack sizes) were retrieved from the symmetry line nodes, and were also recorded in the same array. It is well known that the stresses σ_y at the hole ligament line are higher near the hole and decay as one gets away from the hole border. When applying the stress condition (13), with the equal sign, at each of the fictious crack sizes, the required remote stress will have an inverse behavior, increasing, as one gets away from the hole border. The array has, thus, all the displacement increments (2nd column counting from the left in table in Figure 11a), where the displacements increase from the bottom up to the top line), the respective applied remote load (1st column of the same table), and the stress at the fictious crack line for all the increments and all nodes of that line (remainder of the columns following the 2nd column in the referred table). Increasing values are ordered from the bottom to the top of that array. The stress condition (13) was thus used in each column of latter part of the table. A polynomial interpolation was made to find the respective remote stress σ_∞ and u_{nom} . This was done for each crack, being the locus of the stress condition points, the increasing stress criterion curve superimposed on the table, on Figure 11a).

Energy criterion:

The basis of the energy criterion is the calculation of the instantaneous decrease of the stored elastic strain energy, $\Delta\Pi$, condition (14), due to the cracks onset at the hole border. In the present viscoelastic case, it is calculated, as mentioned, by the Crack Closure Integral Method. In this method, the instantaneous decrease of the stored elastic strain energy is calculated by computing the work at the crack, carried out instantaneously. In our case the method is applied incrementally, being solved for the increasing remote displacements. Following this method, for each diameter and crack, a loop of displacement increments is done. In each loop cycle a fresh study is started in order to erase viscoelastic history effects. At the beginning of the loop, the crack is in closed state (crack nodes are constrained vertically) and its reactions are extracted for that input remote displacement. Then the crack supports are suddenly released and the crack extends, being the displacements of its face

recorded. Finally the crack is closed again suddenly and the closure forces are also retrieved. The initial reactions are taken as a reference only, but we check that they coincide with reactions after the instantaneous release and closure of crack faces. Using the Crack Closure Method, the instantaneous decrease of the stored elastic strain energy of the holed plate, when the crack is extended, is calculated by summing the work of each crack node, which can be accomplished by doing the dot product of the crack closure forces vector obtained the last set, by the crack displacements vector, obtained when it opens. The dot product was divided by a factor of two in order to have the actual linear elastic energy loss. The viscous part does not have influence on this process because the crack is suddenly opened and closed, without enabling the viscous effects to interfere. $\Delta\Pi$ was thus computed for all the displacement increments, for each diameter and crack. It was multiplied by a factor of two, in order to include the energetic effect of the half of lower crack face and plate. The same type of array arrangement with σ_∞ , u_{nom} and $\Delta\Pi$, done for the Stress criterion, was made (Figure 11b)). After, a polynomial interpolation was made for each crack, with the values of $\Delta\Pi$ and using $\Delta\Pi = -G_c\Delta A$, condition (14), and the corresponding critical σ_∞ for each crack size, was found. The locus of the points representing the energetic condition is the curve superimposed on the table. The curve has a descending behavior for increasing crack size and increasing input displacement, because the Energy Release Rate is higher for bigger cracks and remote loads, and when the crack increases, for the same remote stress, the energy loss is higher, but its variation is quadratic in the stress and crack size, as its well known. So, when applying the Energy condition (14), the value of the critical Energy Release Rate G_c multiplied by the crack length, l , needed to be applied to equate $-\Delta\Pi$ is lower than the precedent value for a smaller crack. $\Delta\Pi$ is computed in units of force per unit thickness times the displacement, due to plane stress or plane strain condition.

Coupled Stress and Energy criterion:

The coupled criterion prediction for the critical load is obtained from the intersection of the two locus curves of Figure 11, for each stress and energy condition, yielding the pair σ_∞^c , l_c , for each diameter. Preliminary results for the seven diameters and twenty crack lengths, ranging from 0.01 mm until 0.2 mm, increased by 0.01 mm, were computed and compared with experimental results of hole plates rupture remote stresses in the next section. It should be mentioned that the Crack Closure Method for our FE model was first validated with linear elastic material model and compared with the predictions of the FFM coupled criterion obtained with MathematicaTM code.

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In Figure 12, predictions of the size effect on the critical load, obtained with the FFM+FEM+viscoelastic model and analytical equation for the FFM+Linear Elastic (LE) case solutions, in plane stress, are compared with experimental results.

Figure 12: Comparison of critical remote stress (dimensionless) versus hole diameters: FFM+FEM+viscoelastic, experiments and analytical equation for linear elastic case, plane stress.

It can be seen that the viscoelastic solution correlates better the experimental results than the FFM+LE analytical equation.

The fact that, for bigger hole sizes, the viscoelastic solution is positioned under the linear case solution is due to the finite width size of the plate.

In the future, more Prony terms will be implemented, try the use of pure generalized Maxwell model, having zero equilibrium modulus and is aimed also to study a nonlinear viscoelastic model of the PMMA, in conjunction with the FFM coupled criterion.

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